

The Encoding of Insular Polyphony in English Mensural and Pre-mensural Notations

Karen Desmond

Maynooth University

karen.desmond@mu.ie

Introduction

The Music Encoding Initiative currently has two fairly robust modules for the encoding of vocal repertoire notated in important medieval notation systems, namely the MEI Neumes module (for plainchant) and the MEI Mensural Notation module (for polyphony). Franco's systematic rule-based system for mensural notation made a significant intervention in the history of music when he asserted that the notational symbol (the 'figure') ought to represent a fixed duration. Franco famously wrote that 'since sounds are the cause and principle of the modes, and notes are the signs of sounds, it is obvious that we ought to explain about notes, or about figures, which are the same...A figure is a representation of a sound arranged in one of the modes. From this it follows that the **figures ought to indicate the modes and not, as some have maintained, the contrary**'. Franconian notation is in some ways context-based—meaning that the ultimate rhythmic duration of longs, breves, and semibreves are determined by their position relative to each—but his system outlines a small number of rules that a computer can process relatively easily (for this, see [Thomae 2017](#)).

A significant portion of the western European polyphonic repertoire is notated in notations that preceded Franco's rule-based system that associated fixed durations to specific symbols, including, for example, the Aquitanian and Parisian polyphonic repertoires. BROKENSONG, a five-year project funded by an ERC Consolidator Grant, examines polyphonic singing and written culture in late medieval Britain and Ireland, from c. 1150-c. 1350. As part of the project, the entire extant repertoire is being encoded (approximately 600 compositions, many of them fragmentary, notated in approximately 120 fragmentary manuscript sources). While many compositions are notated in Franconian and extended Franconian notations, a large portion of the repertoire is notated in notations that can be broadly categorized as

either modal, modal with Insular characteristics, and pre-mensural or mensural with Insular characteristics ([Bent](#), [Wibberley](#), [Lefferts](#), [Losseff](#)). These notations are more flexible than standard Franconian notation and frequently informed by local practice. The interpretation may be dependent on notational dialects used in a particular geographic location, or by a particular scribe, or indeed the interpretation may be unclear. In this paper, I introduce two case studies from the BROKENSONG repertoire copied in Insular notation and present some of the most significant issues related to their encoding.

1 Case studies

1.1 *Miro genere* in London, Lambeth Palace, MS 457

The notation of this two-voice conductus has been discussed and edited in several studies (including [Sanders](#), [Losseff](#), [Deeming](#)). The scribe uses two different notational forms for single notes - a virga and a rhomb - but whether these are intended to signify differences in rhythmic duration is a matter of debate. For the notation in the original manuscript, see **Figures 1**. Losseff maintains that this piece defies any attempt to interpret the rhombs as breves (*ibid.*, p. 114) and Deeming edits *Miro genere* using stemless unmeasured noteheads aligned in score; Sanders offers a more definitive rhythmic interpretation. Pieces like *Miro genere* have aspects that potentially could be accommodated by the syllable-based focus of the MEI neumes module, where the encoding of polyphonic voices could be aligned according to the syllables of the underlaid text, without necessarily having to force a modern rhythmic interpretation upon it. As the MEI Guidelines for the element <syllable> state: ‘Neume notation can be thought of as “neumed text”. Therefore, the syllable element provides high-level organization in this repertoire’. The text has a similar high-level organizational function in pre-mensural notation of music that early theorists designated as ‘cum littera’ (‘with words’), as in this conductus example.

1.2 *Ave tuos benedic* and *Ave Maria salus hominem* in Oxford, Worcester College, MS 213*

On the other hand, the compositions in Oxford, Worcester College, MS 213* are in a transitional notation that approaches a common notation type in Insular sources, where the virga and rhomb definitively indicate long and short rhythmic durations respectively (see Figure 2). Modern scholarship has termed this type of notation ‘English Mensural Notation’ (EMN) since it, like Franco’s system, associates fixed durations with specific notational symbols. Again, however, like Franco’s system, elements of a context-based system are found in EMN. In this case study, I outline the rules base for EMN, and discuss how a @notationsubtype (=‘EMN’) of the Mensural Notation module’s @notationtype could potentially accommodate this particular ‘flavour’ of mensural notation.

Figure 1: The beginning of *Miro genere*, in two-part score. London, Lambeth Palace, MS 457, fol. 192r (detail).

Figure 2. *Ave tuos benedic*, Oxford, Worcester College, MS 213*, fol. 1v (detail)

Conclusion

A key activity of the BROKENSONG project is to work with the MEI Community to develop encoding standards for these Insular notations that are flexible enough to capture the basic meaning of the signs (especially so that polyphonic voice parts can be aligned correctly), but also specific enough to capture nuances of scribal habit or notational dialects.

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References

- Bent, M. (1978). A Preliminary Assessment of the Independence of English Trecento Notation. In Agostino Ziino, ed., *Ars nova Italiana del Trecento*, 4., pp. 65–82. Certaldo.
- Deeming, H., ed. (2013). *Songs in British Sources c. 1150-1300*. *Musica Britannica*, 95. Stainer and Bell.
- Lefferts, P. M. (1986). *The Motet in England in the Fourteenth Century*. University of Michigan Press.
- Losseff, N. (1994). *The Best Concords: Polyphonic Music in Thirteenth-century Britain*. Garland Publishing.
- Thomae, M. E. (2017). *Automatic Scoring Up of Mensural Music Using Perfect Mensurations, 1300-1350*. [MA thesis: McGill University].
- Sanders, E. H., ed. (1979). *English Music of the Thirteenth and Early Fourteenth Centuries. Polyphonic Music of the Fourteenth Century*, 14. Monaco.
- Wibberley, R. (1975). *English Polyphonic Music of the Late Thirteenth and Early Fourteenth Centuries: A Reconstruction, Transcription and Commentary*. [Ph.D. diss., Oxford University].